

A LOCAL PERSPECTIVE: CONFUCIUS INSTITUTES IN CHILE

Sophia Acevedo & Daniela Hernández

June 22, 2024.

This project was carried out by the Millennium Nucleus on the Impacts of China in Latin America (ICLAC). ICLAC is funded by the Millennium Science Initiative of the National Agency for Research and Development (ANID) and is hosted by the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Universidad de Chile, Universidad Católica del Norte, and Universidad de Tarapacá.

The opinions expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the authors.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20614443

How to cite: Acevedo, S. & Hernández, D. (2024). A Local Perspective: Confucius Institutes in Chile. ICLAC. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20614443

Research team

Sophia Acevedo and Daniela Hernández

Design and layout

Pedro Díaz

Millennium Nucleus on the Impacts of China in Latin America (ICLAC).
www.iclac.cl

The Millennium Nucleus ICLAC wishes to thank the Embassy of Canada to Chile for supporting the English translation of this case report.

Index

5

Abstract

7

1. Contextualization: Confucius Institutes, Origins, Critiques, and Debates Surrounding Soft Power

8

2. Objectives and Methodology

9

3. Confucius Institutes: Challenges and Opportunities for a Bi-Regional Organization

14

4. Organizational Profiles of the Confucius Institutes: Distinctions and Specificities among the Chilean Cis

15

5. Everyday Practices and Participant Motivations in the Chilean Confucius Institutes

18

6. From Cultural Essentialism to Intercultural Tolerance: Chilean Confucius Institutes as Bridges to Understand Differences

19

7. Perceptions of Soft Power: Confucius Institutes as Instruments of China's International Policy

20

8. Conclusions and Research Challenges

22

9. References

Abstract

China's position as Chile's primary trading partner has prompted extensive analysis of the economic and diplomatic dimensions of Sino-Chilean relations. However, it is equally important to examine the spaces where cultural and interpersonal exchange takes place, particularly within institutions such as the Confucius Institutes. This study focuses on the Confucius Institutes in Chile and explores their role as bi-regional organizations within the broader framework of Sino-Chilean relations. While much attention has been given to trade and diplomacy, this analysis seeks to understand how these Institutes facilitate cultural and interpersonal exchange between the two countries. The research is based on 19 semi-structured qualitative interviews, complemented by participant and non-participant observation of various activities organized by Chilean Confucius Institutes. This methodological approach allows for an examination of both the educational and cultural dimensions of these institutions. The study contributes to existing scholarship by adopting an anthropological perspective that highlights the bi-regional character of the Institutes and the challenges they encounter within a dual governance structure. It also underscores the importance of understanding how Confucius Institutes are perceived and received across diverse political and cultural contexts. In the Chilean case, Confucius Institutes generate not only linguistic and cultural impact, reflected in the growing number of students interested in learning Mandarin, but also serve as spaces of intercultural mediation. Their capacity to adapt to local contexts is central to their role as facilitators of cultural exchange and to the development of intercultural perspectives.

1. Contextualization: Confucius Institutes, Origins, Critiques, and Debates Surrounding Soft Power

Confucius Institutes are a global initiative launched in 2004 by the Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, hereafter China or the PRC. Named after one of China's most influential thinkers, the Institutes are overseen by the Chinese International Education Foundation, CIEF, formerly Hanban, and supported by the Centre for Language Education and Cooperation, CLEC. CLEC is primarily responsible for training Chinese language teachers and promoting Mandarin worldwide. While Confucius Institutes are closely linked to CIEF in terms of funding and curricular content, CLEC presents itself more broadly as a support body for institutions that promote Mandarin, not exclusively for Confucius Institutes. Today, the initiative includes more than 500 Confucius Institutes and approximately 800 Confucius Classrooms worldwide, with academic support from numerous Chinese universities.

Despite their global expansion and their contribution to the dissemination of Chinese language and culture, Confucius Institutes have faced significant criticism. In the United States and several European countries, they have been subject to public and political scrutiny, with accusations that they function as vehicles of political propaganda or even espionage. These concerns have extended beyond media debates to institutional

and governmental levels. In 2020, the United States Department of State designated Confucius Institutes and Confucius Classrooms as a foreign mission of the Chinese Communist Party. As a result, more than 111 Confucius Institutes have closed in the United States in recent years. In Germany, the Minister of Education publicly expressed concern about China's influence in German universities and called for clear limits on what was described as the political exploitation of Confucius Institutes. In Spain, social and human rights organizations raised similar concerns, leading to the creation of the platform Stop Confucius Institutes. This group argues that the Institutes undermine academic autonomy and freedom by promoting an official agenda aligned with an authoritarian regime.

In Chile, there are currently three Confucius Institutes: the Confucius Institute at the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile in Santiago, the Confucius Institute Santo Tomás in Viña del Mar, and the Confucius Institute at the Universidad de La Frontera in Temuco. Although each institute has distinct emphases and institutional characteristics, all share the common objective of promoting Chinese language and culture in Chile.

Within the broader national effort to strengthen diplomatic relations with the PRC—now Chile's principal trading partner—it is necessary to examine how Confucius Institutes are embedded in the Chilean context. Often described as one of the most visible soft power initiatives of the PRC, these institutes constitute the central focus of this case study. While they operate through relatively standardized organizational structures and similar institutional models, and thus function as strategic spaces for

shaping favorable perceptions and imaginaries about China, their reception among the broader population is shaped by multiple contextual factors. These include the social, political, economic, and diplomatic environments in which they operate. At the same time, the agency, motivations, and interests of those involved, including directors, administrative staff, teachers, and students, play a decisive role in shaping the internal dynamics of each institute. Confucius Institutes should therefore be examined not only as instruments of international policy but also, following Hubbert, as spaces characterized by contingent outcomes of relationality between nation-states, whose ontologies and epistemologies are equally shaped by the cultural norms through which they are constructed.

8

2. Objectives and Methodology

The primary objective of this case study is to characterize the process through which the three Chilean Confucius Institutes—UC, UST, and UFRO—are co-constructed as organizational projects. To guide this inquiry, four specific objectives were defined: (a) to identify the organizational structure of the Confucius Institutes in Chile; (b) to describe the organizational profile developed by each institute; (c) to examine the everyday practices and motivations of the actors involved in their co-construction; and (d) to compare the organizational profiles, as well as the agency-related and motivational dimensions, across the three centers.

To address these objectives, the study employed a qualitative research design based on semi-structured interviews and both participant and non-participant observation. This observation was conducted across a range of settings, including formal class sessions and extracurricular cultural activities. In total, nineteen interviews were carried out: seven with administrative staff; five with teachers, including two

Chinese nationals; five with students; and two with former students. Seventeen interviews were carried out virtually and two in person. Most interviews were conducted in Spanish, except for one that was conducted in English. Participants were affiliated with ICUC, ICST, ICUFRO, and CLEC. In addition, fourteen instances of observation were recorded. These included eight synchronous virtual activities, five asynchronous virtual activities, and one in-person activity. The observed activities included five class sessions, two roundtable discussions, two lectures, three meetings with administrative staff, and one conference.

Fieldwork was conducted between August and November 2023. During this period, the nineteen semi-structured interviews and fourteen instances of participant and non-participant observation described above were completed. It is important to clarify that, in seeking to understand the internal functioning of the Confucius Institutes, this research draws on the discourses and lived experiences of individuals who participate in the Institutes and in CLEC. Consequently, the perspectives presented in this case study are shaped by the viewpoints of those directly involved in these institutions and may therefore differ from those of the broader Chilean public.

3. Confucius Institutes: Challenges and Opportunities for a Bi-Regional Organization

As reflected in the general organizational structure of Confucius Institutes in Chile, illustrated in the corresponding diagram, the three institutes examined in this study share a common structural model. Each institute is established through an agreement between a Chinese university and a local university in the host country. Although this dual institutional arrangement is foundational to their design, it also generates practical challenges. In particular, the internal bureaucratic procedures of each local university can affect the functioning and decision-making processes of the Institutes. Leadership within each Confucius Institute is shared between two directors: one appointed by the Chinese partner university and one by the local university. In addition, each institute has an administrative team, the size of which varies depending on the host institution, as well as two groups of teachers—Chinese teachers and local teachers. The presence of local teachers plays a key role in ensuring institutional continuity, in contrast with the regular turnover of Chinese teachers, who typically remain in Chile for a two-year period. The coexistence of these different actors, combined with the shared leadership model, shapes the Institutes' internal dynamics. For these reasons, Confucius Institutes in Chile cannot be understood simply as Chinese organizations operating within Chilean territory. Rather, at a structural level, they are configured as bi-regional organizations, characterized by intercultural teams and by the administrative and organizational challenges inherent in dual governance.

3.1. Organizational Structure of Confucius Institutes in Chile

Although a general organizational structure can be identified across the three Confucius Institutes in

Chile, each institute presents distinct characteristics. In the case of ICUC, the institute is composed of twelve individuals: one executive director, one academic director, one administrative assistant, one community manager, three Chilean teachers—who also assume additional responsibilities such as academic coordination, community outreach, and Taiji (Taichi) instruction—two locally hired Chinese teachers, and two teachers appointed by the Chinese partner institution.

A distinctive feature of ICUC's organizational structure is the central role played by the academic director appointed by the Chinese counterpart. As one teacher explained, "basically, the Confucius Institute is her, the academic director." Unlike other Chinese academic directors, who generally remain in Chile for shorter periods, ICUC's academic director has held the position for eight years. This continuity has contributed to the institute's consolidation and institutional stability, despite operating with a smaller team compared to centers such as ICST. At the same time, this prolonged tenure has fostered a more personalized and embodied style of leadership.

ICUFRO, on the other hand, is currently composed of a team of ten individuals. Six perform administrative functions—including the director, coordinator, journalist, and designer—while four are responsible for academic roles: the Chinese academic director, two Chinese teachers, and one volunteer teacher. ICUFRO has faced particular challenges in its consolidation, as it was established during the COVID-19 pandemic. This context disrupted organizational workflows and even affected the ability of the Chinese director and teachers to travel to Chile.

At ICST, nine individuals hold administrative positions, and twenty-seven teachers are employed, some of whom do not work full time at the institute. These teachers are classified as local teachers, native teachers, or international teachers. Operating largely in a virtual format, the administrative team functions through working groups organized around specific areas, including cultural programming, curriculum development, and budgeting, among others.

At a broader structural level, Confucius Institutes face what has been described as the issue of “two heads,” referring primarily to the shared directorship model. The presence of two directors in each institute necessitates continuous internal negotiation, clear differentiation of roles and responsibilities, and effective coordination of an intercultural team under a unified direction. As one interviewee noted:

“The other issue is hierarchy. You have to work with the leaders, so to speak, and they need to delegate decisions, because it will not happen otherwise. So, I have had to work a great deal on that so that it does not feel like an organization with two heads, but rather one with a single head. They have different roles, and they are complementary, but there is one direction and one (administrative) team.”

3.2. Flexibility and Autonomy: Perceptions Regarding the Possibility of Staff Influence in the Organizational Projects of Confucius Institutes

Although a relatively established organizational structure exists, Confucius Institutes operate within a minimalist and flexible framework. There are no prescribed procedures regulating rituals, practices, discourses, narratives, or other aspects of everyday life. Nor are there mandatory content guidelines, fixed curricula, or predetermined class formats. The implementation of this structure is primarily guided, adjusted, and reassessed by directors, organizational staff, and teachers within each institute, while students’

Diagram 1

General organizational structure scheme of Chilean CI’s

suggestions tend to play a more limited role in shaping institutional direction.

The findings indicate that, for administrative staff and directors, agency is shaped by the overarching objectives of the Confucius Institutes, the availability of resources, and the alignment of proposed activities with annual planning. Teachers' agency, in turn, depends on approval from organizational and leadership teams, who nonetheless allow flexibility in adapting teaching materials and class content to students' needs. Students exercise influence through formal feedback mechanisms such as surveys and meetings, as well as through direct contact with teachers, administrative staff, and, in some cases, directors.

These dynamics reveal the existence of spaces for organizational adjustment, flexibility, and even innovation. Administrative staff and directors consistently report that their decision-making is not constrained by China, and that they are free to act provided their initiatives do not conflict with the shared objective of all Confucius Institutes, namely the teaching of Chinese language and culture:

"I have not felt constrained, because I believe there is clarity regarding the purpose of the Institute. So, one does not engage in issues that might generate conflict. In general terms, I would say that the things we have wanted to do and propose, we have always done. I would say that at no point have we felt that there were things coming from China telling us that something could not be done."
(Administrative staff member)

Although constant communication exists between both leadership counterparts, it does not take the form of directives or demands. Rather, it operates as collaborative coordination grounded in mutual trust. Directors and administrative staff express confidence that they understand the institutional objectives and that they will neither propose nor authorize activities that contradict those objectives. While this dynamic

could be interpreted as a form of self-limitation, participants do not conceptualize it in those terms.

This idea becomes particularly visible when addressing potentially controversial issues related to China, such as matters concerning Tibet and Taiwan, or when seeking to protect the public image of the institutes by avoiding politicized content that could damage their reputation. The pursuit of what participants describe as "political neutrality" reflects awareness of the controversial perceptions sometimes surrounding Confucius Institutes, especially in comparison with other language institutes worldwide, and a desire to prevent negative consequences. As one administrative staff member explained:

"I have never seen a director of the Alliance Française speak about Emmanuel Macron's politics in France. I have never heard the director of the Goethe Institute talk about the problems in Germany with strikes or Germany's position in the European Union. That is something that must be maintained. Even if it is true that the structure of the Confucius Institute is an alliance with a Chinese counterpart, where there are suspicions, and I would say unfounded suspicions (...) we must be very careful about what we offer. We offer language and culture, and that is where we remain."

On the one hand, Confucius Institutes appear to allow meaningful degrees of agency and autonomy in the actions of their participants. The institutes are shaped and co-constructed through the decisions and practices of actors whose subjectivities influence organizational outcomes, rather than through a rigid structure that determines those subjectivities. On the other hand, both teachers and students perceive openness to co-construction, understood as the possibility of influencing and being influenced within an ongoing and dynamic process of producing, reproducing, and, at times, subtly reshaping the organization. This dynamic is also reflected in financial governance. As one teacher explained:

“Each university, meaning the Chinese counterpart that has agreements with the universities here, used to receive funding distributed by Hanban for each Confucius Institute. I believe it was in 2020 that Hanban was dissolved and CLEC and CIEF were created. Now, technically, all the financial resources that come from China to the university here are provided directly by the Chinese universities themselves. This has changed things considerably, because Confucius Institutes now have to create courses in order to sustain themselves and pay teachers, since they need to balance their budgets with the funds they receive from China. The academic component depends on CLEC, which oversees teacher training, scholarships, and related matters. Each Confucius Institute here must prepare an annual budget and financial report, which is then sent to China for evaluation. Based on that evaluation, funds, teachers, and other resources are allocated. It is a collaborative effort among all parties: the university there, CLEC, the university here, and the Confucius Institutes themselves, since (it) all depend on multiple factors.” (Teacher).

12

The information collected suggests that the allocation of funds is linked to the approval or rejection of projects, a responsibility that lies primarily with the administrative team and, in particular, with the directors. Although a degree of relative flexibility in the use of funds is acknowledged, influence over their allocation appears limited. The testimony cited above provides the most detailed available account of funding management, which led to the decision not to examine this dimension further in the present study.

3.3. Adaptation to the Local Context: Challenges Surrounding the Institutes as Intercultural Projects

The adaptation of Confucius Institutes to local contexts and to students’ needs constitutes a central

organizational challenge, while also representing an opportunity for culturally relevant integration in Chile. Evidence from the fieldwork indicates that several participants, including both teachers and students, perceive Chilean Confucius Institutes as partially disconnected from Chilean and Latin American cultural realities. In their view, the institutes appear to be conceived and designed for a different audience. This perception is reflected in educational materials that do not always align with the Latin American cultural context and in institutional practices that do not fully accommodate local idiosyncrasies, such as scheduling classes on a public holiday.

In response to these tensions, Chilean teachers are required to develop both individual and collective strategies to adapt institutional content and pedagogical approaches to Chilean society. This cultural and pedagogical misalignment, attributed in part to limited knowledge in China about Latin America and Chile, presents a significant challenge for both administrators and teachers. They must negotiate the parameters of institutional transformation, balancing adaptation to local expectations with the preservation of core objectives. At the same time, they are expected to adjust teaching methods to align with the learning approaches commonly anticipated by Chilean students and, in several cases, by Latin American students more broadly. The origins of this mismatch are generally understood to stem from limited awareness in China regarding the specific social and educational contexts of Latin America and Chile. As a result, educational products and services developed in China, such as master’s programs in teaching Mandarin as a foreign language and instructional materials designed for Spanish-speaking learners, do not always sufficiently account for the contexts in which instruction ultimately occurs.

Effective learning also depends on appropriate pedagogical strategies. Some students report being motivated by the integration of cultural topics into language instruction, while others emphasize the importance of teachers’ strong command of Spanish.

Even within the same course, students may express divergent preferences regarding the level of Spanish proficiency expected of instructors, depending on their individual learning needs. In addition, participants have offered suggestions not only concerning language instruction but also regarding the institutional environment, evaluation methods, and extracurricular programming. These suggestions have contributed to the development of initiatives more closely aligned with students' interests, including webinars on airport vocabulary and lectures on technology. However, they have also generated criticism. Some participants expressed concern about the limited attention given to political and historical topics, as well as the absence of courses focused on Chinese philosophy.

4. Organizational Profiles of the Confucius Institutes: Distinctions and Specificities among the Chilean CIs

Although Confucius Institutes share a common structural model, each institute exhibits distinctive characteristics that differentiate it from the others. It is therefore important to examine how they co-produce what may be described as editorial lines shaped by their respective local contexts. For the purposes of this study, this process is conceptualized as the formation of organizational profiles. Differentiation occurs in at least two ways. First, it emerges through the performance and attribution, not always deliberately, of defining traits associated with each host university. Second, it develops in response to the interests of directors and the needs of students. Together, these elements support the characterization of Chilean Confucius Institutes as projects that are co-constructed and continuously adapted according to the subjectivities of the actors involved in their development. While similar dynamics may be observable in Confucius Institutes in other national contexts, this study focuses exclusively on the Chilean case.

According to interviewees, ICUC is distinguished by a stronger academic orientation. It is perceived as compensating for a relative scarcity of cultural programming with high educational quality, a characteristic linked to its association with the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile and the university's reputation for academic excellence. This institutional affiliation also entails a greater emphasis on research engagement. Additionally, ICUC is described as well connected to key actors within the Sino-Chilean sphere, including the Chinese Embassy in Chile. This

positioning reinforces its image as a space with strong diplomatic linkages and as a platform for institutional networking.

ICUFRO's organizational profile is closely tied to the local context of the Araucanía region. Administrative staff view the institute as an opportunity within a socioeconomically vulnerable environment. The public and regional character of the Universidad de La Frontera is reflected in ICUFRO's emphasis on accessibility, with tuition-free access identified as a central mechanism for expanding opportunities to learn Mandarin. Administrators and teachers consistently describe ICUFRO as an institute still undergoing consolidation and institutional development.

In the case of ICST, its organizational profile is strongly associated with cultural programming. This is reflected in the extensive number of cultural activities organized each year, including lectures, webinars, workshops, and celebrations. Most of these activities are open to the public and are highly valued by students across all Confucius Institutes. Another defining characteristic is ICST's strategic use of virtual platforms. Significant efforts have been invested in innovation and content creation, which have contributed to revitalizing Mandarin instruction and expanding access to participants from other regions and even other countries. Finally, administrative staff emphasize the particular profile of ICST students, for whom learning Mandarin and building networks within the institute may represent a meaningful opportunity for social mobility.

5. Everyday Practices and Participant Motivations in the Chilean Confucius Institutes

To develop a more comprehensive understanding of the Chilean Confucius Institutes, it is necessary to examine the everyday and relational dimensions that contribute to their co-construction as organizations. One of the most salient findings is the strong perception of community surrounding the Institutes, an element consistently valued by participants. Although different terms are used to describe this sense of belonging, there is a shared understanding that the Institutes provide a supportive environment for building relationships with others who also share an interest in China. These relationships may take the form of friendships, family-like bonds, or professional networks.

First, regarding friendships, they emerge prominently among students, for whom the Institute functions as a space to establish connections with peers who share similar interests. The depth and intimacy of these friendships vary according to individual circumstances, but several practices were identified as facilitating their formation. These include the personal initiative of certain students in promoting interaction among classmates, intentional efforts by teachers to encourage interpersonal engagement, and the strengthening of bonds through shared experiences such as summer schools.

Second, participants also frequently invoke the notion of "family" or a "family-like" environment to describe the atmosphere within the Institutes. In some cases, the term refers broadly to a welcoming and pleasant environment. In other instances, it denotes relationships characterized by mutual trust and

conviviality among administrative staff and teachers, understood metaphorically in familial terms. This does not imply the absence of internal tensions. Rather, conflicts are perceived as a natural component of such close relational dynamics.

Third, several participants describe the Confucius Institute community as a space for networking, where professional connections coexist with and often reinforce personal relationships. One participant employed the concept of 关系, *guānxi*, to explain how networks are formed within the Institutes. *Guānxi* occupies a central place in Chinese society and can be understood as a social mechanism through which relationships of familiarity generate reciprocal exchanges of favors and support beyond the domestic sphere. In the case of Chilean teachers, *guānxi* is closely linked to professional development. Several Chilean teachers interviewed, who are not native Mandarin speakers, were previously students at the same Confucius Institutes where they are now employed. Their trajectories illustrate how participation in these networks has shaped their academic and professional paths.

A second major finding concerns the diverse motivations that lead students to study Mandarin Chinese at Confucius Institutes. Many students begin their studies without prior knowledge of the language. Frequently, they already possess an interest in Asia and in other Asian languages, such as Korean or Japanese. This broader interest is often combined with a desire to acquire a new language, motivated in many cases by perceptions of a competitive labor market in which mastery of a third language, after English, may constitute a valuable asset. For other students, however, the decision to learn Mandarin is not primarily pragmatic. Instead, it reflects an intrinsic interest in language learning or in expanding their linguistic repertoire.

Within this broader context of curiosity about Asia and openness to new languages, students often become increasingly aware of China's growing significance in the global geopolitical order, which further influences their decision to study Mandarin. A key pragmatic factor is the cost of enrollment, as Confucius Institutes are widely perceived as more affordable than other language institutions. This consideration is particularly relevant given that many students are also enrolled in university programs. The relative affordability of the Institutes, combined with the agreements and benefits available to students, enhances their attractiveness. Moreover, they represent one of the few accessible opportunities to study Chinese in the country¹.

Once enrolled, students frequently develop additional pragmatic motivations², as new opportunities become visible, such as Confucius Institute scholarships, or scholarships offered by the Chinese government of which they were previously unaware. Although pragmatic considerations are relevant, they are rarely the primary reason for initiating Mandarin studies and tend instead to emerge during the learning process. Personal development motivations remain significant,

1 It is important to note that Chile has been a pioneer in Latin America in implementing the "Teaching the Chinese Language" project within the framework of the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation Forum summit (2004). Furthermore, in 2017, the "Collaboration Agreement between the Ministry of Education and the Regional Center of Confucius Institutes for Latin America (CRICAL)" was approved with the aim of strengthening educational and cultural collaboration between China and Chile at the level of the education system. In 2018, 2200 students from 16 educational institutions studied Chinese through the program (Ministry of Education, 2018).

2 In this case study, "pragmatic motivations" are distinguished from "personal development motivations." The former refer to motivations of a more material nature, such as scholarships, jobs, travel, etc. The latter refer to motivations of a personal nature, such as interest in Chinese culture, language learning, the educational community, and/or strengthening lost ancestral ties, among others.

including the desire to connect with like-minded peers, to challenge oneself by learning what is often described as one of the most difficult languages in the world, and to expand one's knowledge of Asian and Chinese cultures.

Beyond these personal development motivations, a final finding emerging from everyday practices concerns the role of cultural frictions in fostering flexible and adaptive communicative skills grounded in intercultural understanding. These dynamics reflect the emergence of what has been described as a third culture. In 1990, Mike Featherstone introduced the concept of third culture to describe situations in which groups experience communication difficulties due to cultural differences and must learn to coexist despite those challenges. This process may give rise to translocal identities characterized by adaptability and flexibility, sometimes formed at the intersection of multiple identities, thereby reshaping traditional identity frameworks in response to globalization.

An illustrative example is provided by an administrative staff member who explained that, during the pandemic, he joined a team in which he was the only Chilean. As a result, he had to cultivate an openness to difference in order to function within a context that:

"(...) at the end of the day is an intermediate space. It is neither Chile nor China, and I have to have sufficient mental and emotional openness to adapt to the mental and emotional needs of people who have been educated in radically different ways from mine. In that same process, I am also learning, because you have to be able to recognize a different value system. You have to understand that if a Chinese person raises their voice, it does not necessarily mean they are scolding you, they simply speak loudly. So, in order to work in an international team, you have to be empathetic. It is absolutely necessary, because empathy allows you

to overcome cultural differences." (Administrative staff member)

This and similar accounts suggest that Chilean Confucius Institutes function as spaces in which cultural differences, initially experienced as obstacles to effective communication, become learning opportunities. Participants develop skills and strategies that promote openness to dialogue and facilitate mutual understanding within intercultural communicative processes.

6. From Cultural Essentialism to Intercultural Tolerance: Chilean Confucius Institutes as Bridges to Understand Differences

An examination of the cultural representations circulating within Chilean Confucius Institutes reveals the persistence of a dualistic portrayal of Chinese culture. This portrayal is structured around a contrast between the traditionalism of ancient China and the technological modernity of contemporary China. Although such representations may initially appear to frame culture as bound and static, it may also be argued that this dual perception reflects lived realities within contemporary Chinese society, where tradition and modernity coexist in complex ways.

These representations are not reproduced uncritically. Rather, they are discussed, questioned, and reshaped by actors within the Institutes, who actively negotiate how Chinese culture should be presented. Fieldwork observations indicate that the perspectives of specific individuals, including directors, administrators, and teachers, influence the forms through which culture is conveyed. Several interviewees articulated academically grounded positions that emphasize the importance of teaching Chinese culture in ways that foster deeper understanding of the forms of life that emerge from it, rather than relying on simplified or essentialized depictions.

More importantly, these orientations are not the result of pre-established directives from China. Instead, they arise from the local perspectives of administrators and other actors who participate in shaping cultural representation and pedagogy. This influence becomes visible in concrete decisions, such as rejecting particular visual materials, selecting one calligraphic style over another, proposing workshops on specific themes, or offering more extensive cultural explanations during language classes.

Thus, even when certain representations within Confucius Institutes may tend toward a naturalized understanding of “Chinese culture,” it is ultimately the engagement with deeper cultural dimensions, combined with the experience of working and studying within a bi-regional organizational framework, that

fosters greater mutual understanding. In this context, cultural frictions serve as opportunities for developing the communicative skills necessary for effective intercultural interaction. Such processes contribute to closer engagement with China and help soften the perceived boundary between a “self” and an “other,” as discussed by Abu-Lughod (2012).

As one administrative staff member observed, participation in the Confucius Institutes allows for the development of a more nuanced perspective on otherness, enabling individuals to project themselves into the other and to recognize elements of the other within themselves:

“(...) there are things that sometimes seem absurd or difficult to understand, but that is because we are viewing them through a Western or national worldview. You have to investigate and ask questions, because there are underlying reasons that require respect and understanding. When you put yourself in someone else’s shoes, it allows that person to understand you as well, and dialogue can emerge.” (Administrative staff member)

Beyond static conceptions of culture, Confucius Institutes can therefore be understood as spaces of transcultural learning. Within these spaces, students develop awareness of otherness and cultivate the capacity to sustain forms of tolerance toward difference. The metaphor of the “bridge,” repeatedly invoked by interviewees, captures this dynamic. It characterizes the Institutes not merely as language centers, but as conduits for transcultural learning and for the development of intercultural competencies and perspectives. As one administrator explained:

“(...) ultimately, I do not see the Confucius Institute itself as an end, but as a means. The goal is not simply that people study Chinese. Studying Chinese is a means to communicate with others, to work with others, and to collaborate with others.” (Administrative staff member)

These particular elements are the ones that support the characterization of Confucius Institutes in Chile not only as a bridge between nations, but also as a bridge toward the cultivation of intercultural and international perspectives.

7. Perceptions of Soft Power: Confucius Institutes as Instruments of China's International Policy

Anthropological and academic research on Confucius Institutes has largely developed from a political perspective, within which the concept of soft power, introduced by Nye (1990), occupies a central place. Soft power refers to non-militarized strategies through which states seek to advance their national interests and agendas in the international geopolitical arena. A number of scholars, including Hubbert (2019), Repnikova (2022), Harting (2012), Su-Yan (2013), and Hua and Wei (2014), have analyzed the reception and contestation of Confucius Institutes in various local contexts. In several cases, these institutions have encountered strong resistance, as political interpretations of their presence have generated suspicion and concern regarding the nature and intentions of their educational projects.

A notable difference between the Chilean case and much of the existing literature lies in how the political dimension of Confucius Institutes is addressed. In a significant portion of academic scholarship, the political character of these institutions is treated as self-evident, and they are readily framed as instruments of soft power. In contrast, many participants within Confucius Institutes, both in Chile and in other Latin American contexts, express caution about having their organizations labeled as political entities. This concern is particularly salient given the precedent of closures experienced in the United States. These apprehensions became visible during a CLEC-organized seminar titled "The Importance of the Chinese Language and the Role of Confucius Institutes in Education in Mexico and Latin America." During this event, speakers including Roberto La Fontaine, director of CLEC, Rubén Tang, founder of the Confucius Institute at the Pontifical Catholic University of Peru, and Andrés Aluja, director of the Confucius Institute at the Autonomous University of Yucatán, identified political accusations

as a major challenge. Although such accusations have not materialized in Latin America, they were described as a potential risk for the region. The speakers sought to position Confucius Institutes as comparable to other language institutes, while emphasizing the importance of political neutrality and the avoidance of direct involvement in political strategies.

We suggest that these two perspectives can coexist when soft power is understood primarily through an educational lens. Within this framing, Confucius Institutes are perceived as spaces that contribute to improving China's image, and therefore their political implications are not necessarily interpreted negatively. When asked about objectives beyond the official mission of promoting language and culture, several participants acknowledged that Confucius Institutes contribute to enhancing China's image in Chile. Three main strategies were identified in this regard: the teaching of positive aspects of Chinese culture in class, the organization of cultural activities aimed at broader audiences, and the provision of scholarships to students.

Regarding the first strategy, participants emphasized the value of learning about China beyond prevailing stereotypes and stigmas, particularly in contexts where individuals of Chinese nationality or ancestry constitute a minority. For students, this learning process often represents an opportunity to broaden their perspectives and to engage with alternative ways of understanding and living life. Through this process, what initially appears as cultural otherness becomes increasingly familiar. Several participants noted that this deeper knowledge fosters empathy and sympathy toward China and its people, thereby contributing to a more favorable image of the country.

The second strategy concerns the role of cultural programming. There is a widely shared perception that participation in cultural events enhances China's image by offering accessible and often idealized forms of knowledge about the country. In practical terms, both ICST and ICUC have organized numerous open

cultural activities and celebrations that have attracted large audiences. These events have strengthened the Institutes' connections with broader communities beyond their students.

The third strategy relates to scholarships offered by Confucius Institutes and by the Chinese government. Scholarships operate as a material mechanism for shaping perceptions of China, influencing both those who are selected and those who aspire to be selected. Participants who have traveled to China frequently describe a significant transformation in their perceptions of the country after directly experiencing aspects such as technological innovation and historical landscapes, which had previously been conveyed through discourse at the Institutes. This strategy also has a cyclical dimension. Individuals who receive scholarships and pursue studies in China, often in the field of Chinese language teaching, may later return to Chile, become teachers, and transmit their positive experiences and enthusiasm to new cohorts of students. In turn, these students may begin to envision similar trajectories for themselves.

In this sense, when soft power is expressed through the organizational project of the Confucius Institutes by contributing to an improved image of China, it takes on a depoliticized and, in many cases, positive connotation. This is particularly evident when it is associated with tangible benefits such as scholarships, or with social and intellectual gains such as appreciation for cultural diversity and the demystification of racial stereotypes associated with Chinese people. Moreover, participants often become informal ambassadors of the organizational project, sharing the perspectives, knowledge, and experiences they have acquired with individuals outside the Institutes.

8. Conclusions and Areas for Future Research

This case study has characterized the process through which Chilean Confucius Institutes are co-constructed as organizational projects. The findings indicate that these Institutes are composed of individuals who operate within a shared project in which they believe, drawing on the tools, contexts, constraints, and perspectives available to them.

First, according to interviewees, the organizational structure of the Chilean Confucius Institutes functions in a flexible and minimalist manner. This structure allows for adjustments and even spaces for innovation, provided that such modifications align with the Institutes' fixed objectives. Second, the perceived organizational identities of the three Institutes were described in differentiated terms. ICST is commonly associated with a cultural profile, ICUC with a more academic orientation, and ICUFRO with a role as a space of opportunity within a socioeconomically vulnerable context.

The study also explored the subjective and experiential dimensions of participation in the Chilean Institutes, including the multiple understandings of the IC community or communities. Participants actively cultivate friendships, relationships of familiarity, and professional networks. Two primary types of student motivation for learning Mandarin were also identified. The first consists of pragmatic motivations related to scholarships and professional or career opportunities. The second includes personal development motivations linked to interest in Asian culture, language learning as a hobby, and curiosity about Chinese language and culture.

Encounters between different cultural backgrounds often generate tensions and cultural frictions. However, these experiences can become opportunities for developing skills such as empathy, intercultural understanding, and effective communication. In this sense, Confucius Institutes were observed as spaces

of transcultural learning, where students cultivate awareness of otherness and the capacity to sustain tolerance toward difference. These elements support the characterization of the Institutes in Chile not only as a bridge between nations, but also as conduits for the development of intercultural and international perspectives.

With respect to soft power, the concept is widely invoked by participants when describing the global objectives of the Confucius Institutes. Nevertheless, it does not carry a negative connotation associated with indoctrination or censorship. Rather, it is understood as an effort to improve China's image. This objective is generally considered legitimate and, in many cases, positive, particularly in light of what participants perceive as limited knowledge and persistent stereotypes about China outside the IC community.

Several good practices that could enhance reception and engagement emerged during data collection. First, the use of surveys to incorporate student voices into decision-making processes is both valued and desired. However, participants emphasized that collecting feedback must be accompanied by its effective implementation in order to strengthen the educational community. Second, a number of interviewees expressed interest in stronger collaboration among the Chilean Confucius Institutes, including ICUC, ICUFRO, and ICST. Such collaboration could occur at the administrative level, through joint activities, and potentially through broader cooperation at the Latin American level. These aspirations stand in contrast to the current perception of ongoing and, at times, unnecessary competition among the Institutes. Third, there is a positive assessment of integrating cultural content into both extracurricular programming and classroom instruction. Participants view this integration as contributing to a deeper understanding of China and as supporting the development of global competencies, fostering individuals with broader intercultural perspectives.

Finally, three areas for future research were identified, although they fall beyond the scope, subjects, resources, and timeframe of the present study. First, future research could undertake a comparative analysis of perceptions of Chinese soft power alongside those associated with other Asian countries such as Japan and South Korea, whose cultural products enjoy considerable popularity among Chilean youth. Second, further investigation is needed to understand how students in Chilean Confucius Institutes position themselves in relation to more controversial aspects of China, such as censorship. Given that students report encountering contradictory information, it would be valuable to examine how they reconcile these narratives and how such perceptions influence their practices, including efforts to strengthen ties with China. Third, it would be relevant to analyze how Confucius Institutes operate in Latin American countries with less favorable political contexts. Argentina provides a pertinent case following the election of President Javier Milei, who expressed strong criticism of China during his campaign and indicated an intention to sever relations. In a media appearance, he stated: "I do not engage in transactions with communists. We could engage in transactions with the civilized side of life, which is the West" (América Economía, October 24, 2023). Although a complete rupture of economic relations between the two countries appears unlikely, it would be valuable to examine whether and how Confucius Institutes in Argentina are affected by a government that adopts a hostile stance toward China.

9. References

- Abu-lughod, L. (2012). Escribir Contra de la Cultura. *Andamios*, 9(19), 129-157.
- América Economía. (24 de octubre del 2023). Las amenazas de Javier Milei contra China: ¿triunfará la ideología o el pragmatismo en Argentina? *América Economía*. <https://www.americaeconomia.com/economia-y-mercados/las-amenazas-de-javier-milei-contra-china-triunfara-la-ideologia-o-el>.
- Bell, D. (2000). Guanxi: a nesting of groups. *Current Anthropology*, 41(1), 132-138. <https://doi.org/10.1086/300113>.
- Congressional Reaserch Service (2023, febrero). Confucius Institutes in the United States: Selected Issues. Congress.gov. Recuperado 9 de septiembre de 2023, de <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/IF/IF11180>.
- Feuchtwang, S. (2001). Making place: State projects, globalisation and local responses in China. UCL Press.
- Gillman, B. (2022, Junio). „Man darf nicht naiv sein“: Forschungsministerin rät Hochschulen zu radikalem Schritt gegen China. *Handelsblatt*. Recuperado 10 de mayo de 2024, de <https://www.handelsblatt.com/politik/deutschland/bettina-stark-watzinger-im-interview-mandarf-nicht-naiv-sein-forschungsministerin-raet-hochschulen-zu-radikalem-schritt-gegen-china/28430930.html>.
- Hartig, F. (2012). Confucius Institutes and the Rise of China. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 17(1), 53-76. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11366-011-9178-7>.
- Hua, Z., & Wei, L. (2014). Geopolitics and the Changing Hierarchies of the Chinese Language: Implications for Policy and Practice of Chinese Language Teaching in Britain. *The Modern Language Journal*, 98(1), 326-339. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2014.12064>.
- Hubbert, J. (2019). China in the world: an anthropology of Confucius Institutes, soft power, and globalization. University of Hawai'i Press.
- Ministerio de Educación. (2017). Aprueba convenio colaboración entre el Ministerio de Educación y la Fundación Centro Regional de Institutos Confucio para América Latina. Decreto Exento N°1092. Recuperado de http://transparencia.mineduc.cl/terceros_actos_administrativos_aprobatorios.html.
- Ministerio de Educación. (21 de marzo del 2018). Llegan a Chile nuevas docentes nativas de chino mandarín. <https://ingles.mineduc.cl/2018/03/21/llegan-chile-nuevas-docentes-nativas-chino-mandarin/>.
- National Association of Scholars (2023). How many Confucius institutes are in the United States?. https://www.nas.org/blogs/article/how_many_confucius_institutes_are_in_the_united_states.
- Nye, J. S. (1990). Soft Power. *Foreign Policy*, 80, 153-171. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1148580>.
- Repnikova, M. (2022). Rethinking China's Soft Power: "Pragmatic Enticement" of Confucius Institutes in Ethiopia. *The China Quarterly*, 250, 440-463. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0305741022000340>.
- Stop Instituto Confucio. (s.f). Carta abierta. Recuperado 10 de mayo de 2024, de <https://www.stopinstitutoconfucio.com>.
- Su-Yan, P. (2013). Confucius Institute project: China's cultural diplomacy and soft power projection. *Asian Education and Development Studies*, 2(1), 22-33. <https://doi.org/10.1108/20463161311297608> [Paper no gratis]

